

Part IV: Analytical Framework

In this section, I will be analyzing the data collected from Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre* and Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë* and their respective translations. I will give specific examples of elements of style and their translations within the chosen excerpts, followed by their analysis, from both novels. These styles are common to both source texts' authors. For this work, all instances of the novels cannot be examined, but specific excerpts are chosen in order to demonstrate and support my arguments in answering the research questions.

a) Authorial Style of Culture-Bound Terms

Many scholars like Helen Gibson, Yang Yu, and Xiao Hongying (among others) have contributed to the debate about introducing the culture-bound terms, examining how such terms seem challenging to translate. Helen Gibson's work pays attention to the strategies used by the translator to surmount these challenges (80). In the study of Yang Yu and Xiao Hongying, these specific words are referred to as "Culture-loaded words" and "lexical vacancies" because such words are made up of aesthetics and peculiarities that lack an equivalence in the intended culture and linguistic system. They reflect the sociocultural elements of a source community in such a unique way that they have no adequate representation in the sociocultural and linguistic context of the intended audience (413).

And, these lexical vacancies, or culturally loaded words, or, as Helen Gibson calls it, culture-specific language (21), occur throughout Francophone African novels, including in Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre* and Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë*. One of the writers' objectives in using culture-bound terms, arguably, is to magnetize the reader's attention to the source culture and to fascinate the cultural weight and contexts of such terms in the reader's mind

(Hamidouche 158–159). Another function of these terms is to express local, culturally bound realities, perhaps as much for an internal audience as for an external one.

Bâ ST1: Le « Zem-Zem », eau miraculeuse venue des Lieux Saints de l’Islam, pieusement conservée dans chaque famille, n’est pas oublié (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 10).

Bâ TT1: The *Zem-Zem*, the miracle water from the holy places of Islam religiously kept by each family, is not forgotten (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 3).

In the excerpt above, the style of Mariama Bâ highlights the religious word « Zem-Zem » through the quotation mark, an example of a culturally significant term. This emphasizes the general notion that religion is part of a people’s culture. Mariama Bâ, employing « Zem-Zem, » shows how African religious practices are evident in Francophone African literature.

Semantically, the word is a proper noun in Arabic for a well near Mecca that is considered holy by Muslims. The water, in Bâ ST1, is a symbol of spiritual purity, blessing, and faith: those solidify the protagonist’s (and each family’s) spiritual and cultural identity while passing through evil circumstances. This suggests that one of the functions of religion in African culture is as a source of strength and hope, and thus, connecting Mariama Bâ’s audience not only emotionally but also spiritually. In the Bâ ST1, the term « Zem-Zem » is immediately followed by its description or definition, as shown in the excerpt, and the Bâ TT1 preserves the propositional meanings. The definition aims at affirming collective identities, to internal readers, by echoing shared cultural ideas. However, the use of the description or definition in this text can also point to an orientation towards external readers who might not be acquainted with the Islamic practices.

How to properly present the religious nuance tied to the (Francophone) African culture is one of the challenges of translating this excerpt, as this gives room for multiple interpretations of keywords such as « miraculeuse, pieusement, conservée, » which contextualize the significant

nuances of « Zem-Zem » in the author's universe. The « Zem-Zem », placed at the beginning of the sentence, followed by a piece of information about its sense and essence, carries a specific feeling in relation to the Islamic observance in Mariama Bâ's community. This could be a sensitive context that should be represented in the target text. As part of Islam, the term « Zem-Zem » has a transnational and translingual presence that creates straightforward translational equivalents. It is a loanword in French, as it is in Wolof and in English.

Since the equivalent exists in English, the mediator stays faithful to the original, exposing the English-speaking audience to the cultural identity seen in the Bâ ST1. The translator as a mediator is therefore taking a step to link the target readership directly to the source text. However, a significant aspect to consider is perhaps whether Bâ's readers, in French or in English, are aware of the significance of the term, especially those who are foreign to Islam. While the Bâ TT1 above presents an instance where style is respected, it can be compared with the translation below, which presents a foreignization of the stylistic feature in the Bâ ST1.

Bâ ST1: « Je ne comprends pas. » Elles non plus ne comprenaient pas l'entrée de Modou, une « personnalité », dans cette famille de « ndol » ^(Pauvres), d'une extrême pauvreté (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 59).

Bâ TT1: 'I don't understand.' They did not understand either the entrance of Modou, a 'personality', into this extremely poor family (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 40).

In the Bâ ST1 above, the word « ndol », equally placed in quotation marks, is consciously used by Mariama Bâ as a cultural referent peculiar to her societal background. This could be another attempt made by her to connect her French audience to her universe through the Bâ ST1. Conveying a sociocultural significance, the term semantically signals a deeper meaning than can be expressed as simply as "poor." And, beyond an economic description, the meaning of « ndol »

involves an inherent reality of poverty, or what I can call an existential situation of life, shaped by poverty. Such a situation could be identified sometimes with the lower social class, in terms of lack of power and access to resources, within the sociocultural context.

The cultural term « ndol » is not an English term; it is, therefore, difficult to translate literally or directly. Mariama Bâ, in the Bâ ST1, decides to leave this Wolof term in quotes and provides a footnote to briefly indicate its sense. First, the translator is faced with variable options: he or she can decide to domesticate this Wolof word and translate its footnote, or vice versa. He or she can foreignize the Wolof word and translate its footnote or vice versa. Also, he or she can foreignize or domesticate this term without a footnote. And, lastly, the translator chooses to translate just the footnote made by the original author. This is just as important as the nuances of the word. Part of the experience of the French text is an encounter with Wolof, and the question, again, is whether the French reader grasps all the sociocultural nuances of the term.

On the other hand, linguistic encounters of this kind, according to thinkers like Xiaofan Li, are at best superficial and at worst exoticizing (192). The translator, therefore, tries to present the target version as more readable by not emphasizing the appearance of « ndol » in the target version: the translator only presents the meaning of such a term to the English audience. The concept of « ndol » in the target text does not include any sociocultural nuances connected to the ecologies of the original author. This could be because translating the footnote alone tends to offer a more generalized description; the target audience might not have the possibility of knowing the weight and peculiarities of an original word (omitted by the translator). However, a casual reader of the English version, to some extent, can easily have a general understanding of the translation without any additional knowledge of the original author's sociocultural milieu. The only issue is how not to risk losing the authenticity of the translation.

Naziha Hamidouche have equally identified certain cultural identifiers in Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre*. In her words, Naziha Hamidouche asserts that the terms are selected by Mariama Bâ to convey certain cultural nuances relating to specific cultural referents (158–159). And these culture-bound words are used in the novel to best represent the author's intent in the source text. They remain peculiar to Mariama Bâ's ecologies while, to some degree, lacking a direct equivalence in the target language. Similar terminologies are used in Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë*.

Kane ST2: —Dis-moi, Samba Diallo, qu'est-ce qu'un Diallobé?

Il avait parlé pour dire quelque chose. Le charme se rompit. Samba Diallo éclata de rire.

—Ah, tiens, on t'a parlé de moi... Un Diallobé... Eh, bien, ma famille, les Diallobe, fait partie du peuple des Diallobé. Nous venons des bords d'un grand fleuve. Notre pays s'appelle aussi le Diallobé. Je suis le seul originaire de ce pays, dans la classe de M. N'Diaye. On en profite pour me plaisanter...

— Si tu es Diallobé, pourquoi n'es-tu pas resté dans le pays des Diallobé? (Kane, *L'Aventure ambiguë* 70).

Kane TT2: “Tell me, Samba Diallo,” he ventured, “what is a Diallobé?”

He had spoken for the sake of saying something. The enchantment was shattered. Samba Diallo burst out laughing.

“Ah, they have been talking to you about me. . . . A Diallobé. . . . Well, my family, the Diallobé, belong to the Diallobé people. We come from the banks of a great river. Our country is also called the Diallobé. I am the only one from this country in M. N'Diaye's class. They take advantage of that to joke about me.”

“If you are a Diallobé, why didn’t you stay in the Diallobé country?” (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 58–59).

Throughout the text, Cheikh Kane used the word “Diallobé” as a distinctive cultural identifier. The Kane ST2 not only shows language markers but also a sociocultural identity of the protagonist, conveying information on his family, ethnicity, nation, and geography. The country is called “Diallobé,” and the citizens from the “Diallobé” country are referred to as the “Diallobé.” Perhaps, the protagonist’s name can be considered a derivative of his country’s name: Samba “Diallo” from “Diallobé,” and whereas Diallobé is treated as invariable throughout the text.

Semantically, therefore, “Diallobé” can be said to be a place, a people, a community, and a lineage. Both excerpts reveal a social and ethnic pride, as they (Kane ST2 and Kane TT2) operate with an explanatory mode for an external reader who is foreign to the (West) African ethnolinguistic world. The protagonist is expected to explain himself to a foreigner, like the text explains Africa to the world. This seems to be as didactic as ironic to readers at the same time.

This act of explaining the self is perhaps an instance of a cultural translation in the context of this dialogue. As for internal readers, it is perhaps absurd to define an African identity within the colonial context because such an explanation seems redundant. The translator, however, presents the culturally specific term “Diallobé” consistently, keeping its ethnic and societal nuances. The ethnolinguistic pattern of “the Diallobé ..., the Diallobé people ..., the Diallobé country ...,” is maintained to share the socioculturally nuanced information through the narrative. That demonstrates the foreignization of the “Diallobé” as a style of the author contained in Kane ST2, as against the strategy used in the translation of the Kane ST2 below.

Kane ST2: —Très bien, cela me suffit! Et le visage de Lucienne s’éclaira. Je sais maintenant que ta négritude te tient cœur (Kane, *L’Aventure ambiguë* 155).

Kane TT2: “Very well, that’s enough for me,” and Lucienne’s face brightened. “I know now that your heart is possessed by your being a Negro—your Negroness, if I may coin a word.” (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 141).

In the Kane ST2 above, the speaker employs the culturally and historically complex French term “Négritude,” which came into existence through Francophone African and diaspora writers and scholars like Aimé Césaire, Léopold Senghor, and Léon-Gontran Damas, during the movement of Négritude (Lambert 248). Cheikh Kane, integrating the term “Négritude” consciously into his novel, is perhaps a deeper reverence for the definition of Samba Diallo’s origin and ethnic pride.

The “Négritude,” as used in the Kane ST2, is a culturally loaded expression that carries both literary and socio-political significance, and the excerpts perhaps reveal the protagonist Samba Diallo as one who has consciously embraced his condition of identity. That gestures towards the author’s involvement with societal and cultural movements that recognize the (Francophone) African identity and reclaim selfhood. Semantically, the history of the term here is especially important, since there are not just parallel, but connected movements of Black expression in English and in France before, and leading up to this period. Examples of such movements include the *Négritude* and the *Harlem Renaissance* (among others).

One of the challenges of translating the “Négritude” is the conciseness of its equivalence in a language like English because of the complex cultural historicity, politics, and significant confession of identity that are all embedded in the term. In addition, accurate (re)presentation of the “Négritude” in English without losing the agreeable affirmations of the (Francophone) African pride in context is another possible obstacle. The time of the publication of *L’Aventure ambiguë* is also crucial in this context (i.e., 1961), and “Négritude was born in the 1930s,” as stated in Emily Sheffield’s account (3). The word “Negro” in English is now seen as an artifact of that time. The

English in the Kane TT2 is a fascinating translation because it eschews any attempt at making the Négritude movement known to the English reader, but also gives up on any equivalent English movement! And, instead, it invents a point of origin of identity, with no history: “Negroness, to coin a word.”

Such a strategy of translating « Négritude » can have many effects on the target readership. “Negro–your Negroness” attempts to generate, to some extent, a free flow in the Kane TT2, instead of curiosity or acquaintance with the cultural referents inherent in the « Négritude. » The translator identifies the term and opts for creativity as a means of conveying its heavy weight in the context. While the target text reader might find the translation easy to read, the positive sociocultural and ethnolinguistic affirmations or connotations of the term might not be all present in the reader’s mind. Nevertheless, the translator’s attempt to create a newly coined term, “Negro,” prevents the English readers from feeling absolutely alienated from the original text. While many scholars might prefer to foreignize this term, the mediator’s style here appears more visible through her creativity in adapting the Kane ST2 above.

b) Repetition as an Authorial Style

In Francophone African novels, repetition patterns are one of the common styles displayed by the authors for various reasons. And translating these repetitions by breaking their patterns can create a significant effect on the target readership. In her *Translation and Style*, Jean Boase-Beier accentuates the notion of pattern as a “way of foregrounding” certain specific features of a text, and that altering an existing or potential pattern can lead to a “foregrounding effect” (151). This situation of foregrounding is applicable in the context of repetition. However, Mona Baker et al., in their “Corpus Linguistics and Translation Studies: Implications and Applications,” posit that repetition patterns are rarely observed in translation: they are either avoided or exaggerated. In

their opinion, altering repetition patterns is one of the “universal features” of translation caused by “constraints which are inherent in the translation process itself” (246). They then argue that the change in repetition patterns stands as one of the differences between a source text and its translated version (234). In Francophone African novels, the authorial style is enriched with the classical form of narration accompanied by repetitive nuances that are influenced by the oral tradition, religious background, and other possible factors present in the author’s universe (Kane et al. 14). Below is an example of repetition, and the translation respects the original style.

Bâ ST1: Et je m’interroge. Et je m’interroge. Pourquoi ? Pourquoi Modou s’est-il détaché? Pourquoi a-t-il introduit Binetou entre nous ? ... Je m’interroge (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 83).

Bâ TT1: And I ask myself. I ask myself, why? Why did Modou detach himself? Why did he put Binetou between us? ... I ask myself questions (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 59).

First, in the Bâ ST1 above, the repetition of « Et » emphasizes the weight of the speaker’s curiosity or inquiry, or confusion. The « Et », semantically, indicates an effect cumulation of the speaker’s obsession and emotion. This repetition pattern is modified in the Bâ TT1. One of the challenges in translating the repetitive style is the inability to (re)present it directly in the cultural narrative norms of the English language system, to suggest the meditative mood present in the Bâ ST1. Another challenge is how to retain the weight of the repetition if, by any means, it cannot be observed in the target language.

My second observation is on the repetition of « je m’interroge ». I find the English rhythmic, but differently; it’s through the variations on “I ask myself.” There is a kind of balance in the Bâ TT1, of the phrase “I ask myself” and an additional word: “W+P. P+W. And + I ask myself. I ask myself, why?” (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 59). However, the translational challenge can

be found in the French verb « s’interroger », which does not have an equivalent with the exact same semantic and syntactical qualities in English. « Je m’interroge » is perfectly acceptable as a complete sentence in French, as seen in the Bâ ST1, needing no arguments, whereas “I ask myself” almost always takes an additional argument in an English context.

The translator presents the author’s introspection and persistence that question the unknown, uncertainty, and yet minimize the redundant elements of language in the Bâ TT1. This signals that the mediator understands the Bâ ST1 as the product of Mariama Bâ’s style, influenced by her (Mariama Bâ’s) ecologies, where repetition serves an emphasis on internal issues or conflict. For the excerpts below, the mediator’s intervention is seen in the domestication of the repetitive style of Mariama Bâ in the Bâ ST1.

Bâ ST1: Un taxi hélé! Vite ! Plus vite ! Ma gorge sèche. Dans ma poitrine une boule immobile. Vite! Plus vite! Enfin l’hôpital! L’odeur des suppurations et de l’éther mêlés. L’hôpital! Des visages crispés, une escorte larmoyante de gens connus ou inconnus, témoins malgré eux de l’atroce tragédie (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 8).

Bâ TT1: A taxi quickly hailed! Fast! Fast! Faster still! My throat is dry. There is a rigid lump in my chest. Fast: faster still. At last, the hospital: the mixed smell of suppurations and ether. The hospital–distorted faces, a train of tearful people, known and unknown, witnesses to this awful tragedy (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 2).

In the Bâ ST1 above, Mariama Bâ uses « Vite! » repeatedly, expressing the urgent condition in which the speaker is situated. With a rising tempo, the consecutive use of « Vite! » is then preceded by the adjective « Plus » to express a moment of ascension in the speaker’s tension and anxiety: from « Vite! » to « Plus vite! ». The semantic feature is tightly webbed with the style, as the

protagonist's mind and other happenings at the hospital are expressed by this descriptive and imperative urgency conveyed by both the Bâ ST1 and Bâ TT1.

Through the rhythmic repetition pattern, Mariama Bâ's audience can perhaps perceive sensitivity and time. One of the possible challenges of translating these repetitive elements is how to neither under-translate nor over-translate the author's intent and tempo. The translator is also faced with the choice of an awkward or exaggerated translation. Another aspect to consider is the fragmentation or the shortness of French sentences, which convey remarkable effects in the text, especially in the Bâ ST1.

The translator decides to clearly describe the situation of the speaker through the representation of the speaker's sense of urgency in the Bâ ST1. The author, through the Bâ ST1, reminds the readers about her sociocultural milieu, where orality impacts literature. One of the ways that the translator mirrors Mariama Bâ's orality in the Bâ ST1 is by introducing the adverb "quickly" into the Bâ TT1, thereby reinterpreting the panic and a sharp immediacy of the protagonist's soul and circumstances in the hospital. Another intervention is the redoubling of the sense of the adverb « vite » in Bâ TT1, where the translator presents the "Fast" five times in Bâ TT1 as against the four times appearance of « Vite » in Bâ ST1. Also, the translator amplifies the sense of urgency in Bâ TT1, as a means of drawing the English reader closer enough to the heartbeat of the protagonist in the situation described by the Bâ ST1. The translator achieves this through the introduction of the word "still" following the simple, literal translation of « Plus vite! »: "Faster!" Therefore, the authorial style is adapted in the Bâ TT1. The choice of adaptation here can make the target audience perceive the situation of the speaker as more intense than required, thereby accentuating the weight of the speaker's quest. Similarly, the translation of the Kane ST2 below presents a partial foreignization of Cheikh Kane's stylistic figures in the translation.

Kane ST2: —Je sais aussi qu’il faut le sauver. Il faut construire des demeures solides pour les hommes et il faut sauver Dieu à l’intérieur de ces demeures (Kane, *L’Aventure ambiguë* 21).

Kane TT2: “I know also that He must be saved. We must build solid dwellings for men, and within those dwellings we must save God (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 11).

In the Kane ST2 above, Cheikh Kane uses « il faut » three times, indicating a possible connotation of necessary actions that are deeper than explicitly immediately understandable. There is an effect of ethical imperative made by rhythmic insistence that anchors the solemnity and the significance of the ideas expressed in the Kane ST1. Semantically, within the Kane ST1, « il faut » seems to mirror an ethical mandate and a cultural commitment in the speaker’s community: such commitment as spiritual and physical salvation.

The repetition of the imperative « il faut » combines both form and meaning to showcase reflection. Such repetitions are common in religious settings—like in Cheikh Kane’s universe—and are used to accentuate truths and morals. One of the issues surrounding the translation of this stylistic anchor is the deeper connotations conveyed in the impersonal French verb « falloir », which repeatedly occurs in the Kane ST2. And the translator is expected to assign an agent to the equivalence of the « il faut » in the Kane TT1.

To adapt the Kane ST1 to English, the translator maintains the fluidity, to some extent, as the «il faut» is neutralized into a passive form, not attaching a particular agent to it. For the remaining elements of repetition, the translator attributes verbs to the English personal pronoun “we” in the Kane TT1. The target audience can, therefore, have an impression that the speaker is included in the actions being called for.

c) **Musical/Rhythmic style**

In a literary work, like in the Francophone texts by Mariama Bâ and Cheikh Kane, musical or rhythmic effects contribute to enhancing the audience's aesthetic experience. The authors employ these elements as a means of enhancing the overall narrative flow, mood, and emotional nuances conveyed in the texts through structural and phonetic features. Instances of musicality or rhythms play out throughout the chosen novels. The following is an example of Mariama Bâ's rhythmic style in the Bâ ST1. And the translation respects the original author's style in the rendering.

Bâ ST1: Sa conduite est conditionnée: une belle-sœur ne touche pas la tête d'une épouse qui a été avare, infidèle ou inhospitalière (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 11).

Bâ TT1: Her behaviour is conditioned: no sister-in-law will touch the head of any wife who has been stingy, unfaithful or inhospitable (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 4).

In the excerpt above, Mariama Bâ carefully employs specific diction in the Bâ ST1, which creates a smooth flow, a harmony through the melody of the vowel sounds. The sequence of soft sounds found in the assonance is then complemented by the alliteration in words such as « conduite, conditionnée, touche, tête » in the Bâ ST1. Semantically, this rhythmic style carries the author's spirit, unveiling a sequence of melodic thoughts. The chant-like rhythms produced by the combination of these sounds remind the reader of Mariama Bâ's culture and society, known for its oral storytelling style.

The excerpts reveal a social principle present in the protagonist's culture: "no sister-in-law will touch the head of any wife who has been stingy, unfaithful or inhospitable" (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 4). The musical pattern of the Bâ ST1 echoes the significance of this rule as a socially valued norm of the protagonist. One of the challenges is how to successfully convey the melodic transition between the words and their sounds, as well as the source author's musical mood in the Bâ ST1.

Part of language diversity is the phonetic difference, especially between French and English. And (re)producing an equivalence of the poetic devices, like assonance and alliteration, encountered in a Francophone African novel into another language can be clearly challenging. The translator is hereby faced with the choice of translating thought for thought, words for thoughts, or seeking a strictly linguistic representation of the original author's rhythms.

There is a broad issue: while the translator focuses on preserving the content, the musicality of the Bâ ST1 is rarely transferred into the Bâ TT1 due to structural differences between the French and English phonological systems. However, there remains some alliteration and assonance in the Bâ TT1 (sister, stinky, touch; head, has, inhospitable). Adapting the Bâ ST1 this way does not repeat the original author's exact rhythmic quality and cadence for the readership of the target Bâ TT1. The source text's reader might have a different auditory experience, while the target reader could have an auditory experience present in the original because such rhythms are still recreated using the target language's phonological systems. Such instances recur in the following excerpts, but the translator chooses the domestication strategy to render the rhythmic style.

Bâ ST1: Daba rageait, blessée dans son orgueil. Elle répétait tous les surnoms que Binetou avait donnés à son père : Vieil homme ! Ventru ! Le Vieux !... (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 60).

Bâ TT1: Daba was furious, her pride wounded. She repeated all the nicknames Binetou had given her father: old man, pot-belly, sugar-daddy! ... (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 40).

Again, the Bâ ST1's short sentence or phrasal structure with exclamation marks reveals the intense cadence describing Daba's speech, which mirrors an oral storytelling, shaped by the author's universe. The rhythm in this context evokes a particular state of mind in Daba. Each exclamation mark enriches the lyrical, performative presentation that reveals Daba's emotion. In addition, the

alliteration in « Vieil ... Ventru! » and « Vieux! » contributes to the dramatic flow. This refers, perhaps, to the African oral traditions of women's speech, in which social memories and personal emotions are conveyed in speech through lyrical, repetitive, and rhythmic nuances.

Semantically, the bruised ego of Daba and the social effect of oral insults on an honorable, elderly man are all reflected in the list of nicknames that the speaker repeated in the excerpts. Beyond a mere diction of the speaker, the nicknames are cultural, stylistic nuances, probably revealing a mode of conversation I can call a social verbal challenge. Again, the translator is faced with obstacles such as lyrical representation of Daba's speech in English, but tries to translate the dramatic, intense cadence evident in the speech, the punctuation, and the choice of words.

The translator's main goal, as evident in the Bâ TT1, is not to present a literal translation of the rhythmic and musical effects found in the Bâ ST1. The three exclamation marks present in the Bâ ST1 become just one in the Bâ TT1. Daba's emotional nuance, expressed in the repetition of those nicknames and very strong punctuation, is smoothly presented to the Bâ TT1 readership. Again, examples of domestication strategy continue in the translation of the Kane ST2 below, as the translator, while navigating the various challenges of fidelity and equivalence, prioritizes other effects of the Kane TT2 over the rhythmic style.

Kane ST2: Toujours en considérant l'enfant, il fit une courte prière, mentalement: « Seigneur, n'abandonne jamais l'homme qui s'éveille en cet enfant, que la plus petite mesure de ton empire ne le quitte pas, la plus petite partie du temps... » (Kane, *L'Aventure ambiguë* 16).

Kane TT2: Still looking closely at the child, he made, mentally, a short prayer: "Lord, never forsake the man that is awaking in this child. May the smallest measure of Thy

sovereign authority not leave him, for the smallest instant of time ...” (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 5).

Cheikh Kane’s novel, too, is enriched with inherent rhythm and musicality. In the Kane ST2 above, the structure of the complex French sentence produces a melodic cadence. In addition, the sound devices, such as assonance and alliteration, played out throughout the Kane ST2, creating an emotional introspection of a suitable atmosphere of prayer uttered by Samba Diallo’s master. That could be like an example of the experiences that can be found in the author’s society, where religious performance and recitations are shaped by solemnity and orality.

Building faith and hope, the prayers in the excerpts seem like rising in ascending notes, carrying deep metaphysical concerns and pleas for safety, intimacy, and perpetuity. Semantically, the rhythm emphasizes the sacredness and relevance of the prayers, as structured by the author to transmit values to the child. The translator’s concern is perhaps with the right choice of words to convey the tone in the Kane TT2: whether to use archaic or informal diction to mirror the prayer mood of Samba Diallo’s Master. Also, whether to choose to adapt the sound devices is another question.

While translating the prayer mood using religious terms, the mediator focuses less on the sound devices and the musicality of the Kane ST2. Though the religious terms here are archaic in everyday speech, they continue to be somewhat common in religious discourse, and even more so in the mid-twentieth century, as at when *Ambiguous Adventure* was published. Therefore, the target reader might understand the message of the Kane ST2 because older religious texts still contain an archaic register.

Kane ST2: Il ferma les yeux pour chasser la vision. Vivre dans l'ombre. Vivre humblement et paisiblement, au cœur obscur du monde, de sa substance et de sa sagesse... (Kane, *L'Aventure ambiguë* 82).

Kane TT2: The knight closed his eyes to banish the vision. To live in the shadow, to live humbly and peaceably at the obscure heart of the world, to live from his own substance and his own wisdom. . . . (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 70).

Cheikh Kane's mood seems like a contemplation in the Kane ST2 above. The assonance and alliteration inform the rhythm of the Kane ST2. The lyrical flow, as well as the repetition of « Vivre » enhances the tone. This repetition seems to produce a refrain-like impression that dominates such a contemplative moment, initiating a measured tempo, inspiring the reader to meditate on the semantic features at the end of each sentence.

The semantic functions of the rhythms in these excerpts are metaphysical, examining the status of man at its lowest level, tranquility, darkness, and wisdom. The musicality blends the mood with the orality, all of which plays out in the character's inner being, and then allows the reader to see through the thoughts of the knight.

However, the translator is expected to resolve a syntactical ambiguity of the Kane ST2: this happens if we are to ask a question of what or whom the genitive clause « de sa substance et de sa sagesse » really refers to. Does this genitive clause refer to the world? its « cœur obscur »? Or to « il », the knight? Such instances also show that issues like preserving the Kane ST2's introspective rhythm, as well as the repetitive sound devices, the knight's emotional state, are worth considering. And the translator's innovative choice is perhaps seen in attributing this genitive clause to the knight, using the pronoun "his." This situates the knight right amid his own thoughts, and no external reference is made to anyone else in the vision. It is also a sensitive task to keep the

reflective tone used in the Kane ST2. Another challenge is finding coherent sentences in English that ensure a smooth transition between ideas, as presented in the Kane ST2.

As seen in the Kane TT2, the translator maintains a repetitive structure of certain phrases of the Kane TT2 that reflects the sound devices contained in the Kane ST2. For example, “to live in the shadow, to live humbly and peaceably ...” (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 70). This also tends to reflect the introspection of the knight’s thoughts while closing his eyes. As the translator manipulates the sound devices in search of equivalence, a fluidity is created like that of the Kane ST2; however, with another set of sounds (i.e., those of the target language).

d) Use of Gender-Specific Language

The novelists introduce gender-sensitive terms in their works (un)consciously due to the general claim that language, culture, and religion cannot be separated. The action of using gender-specific terms in the Francophone African novel is tied to the authors’ ecologies. The translator is hereby expected to be aware of the power and ideological relationships existing in the context of the source text (Marino A223) while negotiating meaning. I will apply this perspective to analyze certain excerpts from the selected Francophone African novels.

Bâ ST1: La belle Mosquée « Médinatou-Minaouara » n’était pas encore édiflée à la gloire de l’Islam ; mais, dans le même élan pieux, hommes et femmes priaient en bordure de la route. « Pour se convaincre de la survie des traditions, il faut sortir de Dakar », murmurait Tante Nabou (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 44).

Bâ TT2: The beautiful Medinatou-Minaouara mosque had not yet been built to the glory of Islam, but in the same pious spirit, men and women prayed by the side of the road. ‘You have to come away from Dakar to be convinced of the survival of traditions,’ murmured Aunt Nabou (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 28).

The above Bâ ST1 now represents an instance of the text where Mariama Bâ's style reflects a socially pertinent, gendered social structure. In the Bâ ST1, « hommes » and « femmes » are explicitly spelled out, which does not connote any gender bias. In foreignizing these stylistic features of the Bâ ST1, the translator finds the equivalence of these terms in English without opting for alternatives like “man” or “humanity,” signaling an instance of foreignization; this can be compared with the following Bâ TT1 below, where the author's style is domesticated:

Bâ ST1: Que de générations a vu défiler ce même paysage figé ! Tante Nabou constatait la vulnérabilité des êtres face à l'éternité de la nature. Par sa durée, la nature défie le temps et prend sa revanche sur l'homme (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 43).

Bâ TT1: How many generations has this same unchanging countryside seen glide past! Aunty Nabou acknowledged man's vulnerability in the face of the eternity of nature. By its very duration, nature defies time and takes its revenge on man (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 27).

In the Bâ ST1 above, the word « générations » used by Mariama Bâ is a gender-neutral or gender-inclusive term that does not specify a masculine or feminine concept. The word « Tante » is gender-specific, referring to a woman, translated into English as “Aunty” in the Bâ TT1. Semantically, « l'homme » is arguably a social and cultural masculine concept that is the universal, default male, but can mean the generality of human beings, or humanity, or the male gender. The phrase « les êtres » is a gender-neutral term used in the Bâ ST1. It does not prioritize one gender over the other. This perhaps reveals the social realities of Mariama Bâ's universe.

The English audience of the modern era, where gender neutrality is emphasized, might perceive little or no gender inclusivity in the Bâ TT1. As the meaning of words changes over time, the issue is how to translate the sense of the gender-specific terms into English in such a way that they would remain coherent and semantically valid through different epochs. However, more

immediately, the translators are looking to ensure the success of their texts in the present, as well as satisfy the publisher's requirements at the time of the publication. Such questions might influence the translator's choice of words in adapting the Bâ ST1 into English, as both the « êtres » (human being) and « l'homme » (humankind) become "man" in the Bâ TT1. Instances of foreignizing strategy are often used in the translation of the following excerpts from Cheikh Kane's *Ambiguous Adventure*, as shown in the Kane TT2.

Kane ST2: Le maître croyait profondément que l'adoration de Dieu n'était compatible avec aucune exaltation de l'homme. Or, au fond de toute noblesse, il est un fond de paganisme. La noblesse est l'exaltation de l'homme, la foi est avant tout humilité, sinon humiliation (Kane, *L'Aventure ambiguë* 33).

Kane TT2: The teacher believed profoundly that the adoration of God was not compatible with any exaltation of man. But, at the bottom of all nobility there is a basis of paganism. Nobility is the exaltation of man, faith is before all else humility, if not humiliation (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 23).

In the Kane TT2 above, Cheikh Kane employs the term « homme » repeatedly. Semantically, both terms can point to two contexts: they can indicate gender neutrality, and they can also be perceived to be gender specific. The translator can also view the application of these words in a philosophical context, which aligns with the universal default male gender.

However, as a literary work, the translator must decide whether to translate the philosophical nuance at the expense of a modern gender-neutral context. The translator's choice, as seen in the Kane TT2, is the adaptation of the philosophical context. The target text's reader who is familiar with such context might not consider the gender-specific nuances conveyed in the text.

Kane ST2: —Monsieur le directeur d'école, disait le maître, quelle bonne nouvelle enseignez-vous donc aux fils des hommes pour qu'ils désertent nos foyers ardents au profit de vos écoles? (Kane, *L'Aventure ambiguë* 19).

Kane TT2: "Monsieur School Principal," the teacher was saying, "what new good are you teaching men's sons, to make them desert our glowing hearths for the benefit of your schools?" (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 19).

Cheikh Kane's use of « Monsieur ..., fils ..., hommes ... » and the pronoun « ils » is a deliberate decision in the novel (i.e., a stylistic element), with no intention toward gender bias. Semantically, the terms carry masculine concepts but accentuate the traditional norm of the default male in Cheikh Kane's culture, like the example of Mariama Bâ's excerpts above: a language usage that reflects a reality of the author's universe. However, the Kane ST2 suggests that either only boys were being educated or that only the education of boys, leading to reduced farm labor, was problematic. That could be tied to the history related to children's education in Cheikh Kane's society of that time, and the question remains: how much attention should be paid to the modern context at the expense of historical accuracy, since the translation is not done for only a single epoch?

The translator, however, decides to foreignize the male concept contained in the Kane ST2: « Monsieur » remains untranslated as a way of revealing the sociocultural nuances in Cheikh Kane's style. The term « fils » becomes "sons" in the Kane TT2. To some extent, the translator's use of the phrase "men's sons" appears sharp in the contemporary context, indicating that children, especially male children, belong to the men and not the women. This intervention of the translator in Kane TT2 signals the use of the default male in Cheikh Kane's culture. And the target, English-speaking readership, will equally experience such feelings as are present in the Kane ST2.

e) Punctuation as an Authorial Style

The question of punctuation in writing is one of the sensitive discourses in a translation context. It is controlled by the linguistic rules available in each language. But in addition to these rules, an editor's preferred style or a publisher's guide can influence the punctuation style of a writer or a translator. One of the challenges is whether, after the publication, the punctuation remains as part of the writer's style.

However, I fundamentally contextualize the question of punctuation style—for the sake of the analysis—as displayed in the two selected texts and their translations, with no special reference to the unpublished manuscripts. I acknowledge that the chosen texts and their translations might and must have been influenced by the publisher and/or the editor before their respective publications. In all, for the sake of analysis, I presume the punctuation styles in both texts and their translated versions to belong to the respective writers, and the analyses are tailored towards this presumption.

Every language, like French and English, is known for using punctuation to create effects. Authors employ punctuation to convey a mood, a sequence of interaction, or to define a context (Tanyitiku 3). In this section, I will analyze the selected excerpts from the perspective of punctuation as a tool of aesthetics and communicative peculiarities.

Bâ ST1: Amie, amie, amie! Je t'appelle trois fois. (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 8).

Bâ TT1: My friend, my friend, my friend. I call on you three times. (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 2).

Mariama Bâ, in the Bâ ST1, uses commas after the first two occurrences of « Amie » to exhibit a rhythmic pattern of pause that accentuates the repetitions. And the translator adapts this effect

created by the commas. The third repetition of « Amie! » is closed by an exclamation mark conveying possible emotional intensity in the character's voice.

Semantically, the weight of words or the emotional intensity that is interpretable is embedded in the punctuation. First, the translator must interpret the motive and the motion of the cadence hidden in the call or the repetition of each « Amie » in the Bâ TT1. The Bâ ST1 is made up of simple words and simple sentences. Also, something else worth considering is how to translate the author's spirit without exaggerating.

The translator chooses to create a similar feel for the target reader through the punctuation, and the exclamation mark in the Bâ ST1 becomes a period in the Bâ TT1. Through the domestication of this authorial style, the reader of the target text can figure out any heaviness of mind, or appeal, or other emotional sentiments that are present in the Bâ ST1: the dramatic tone of the Bâ ST1 conveyed by the exclamation mark—which makes an emotional impact on the readership of the Bâ ST1—is perhaps conveyed with this stop or heaviness of the period that came after the third call: “my friend.”

Bâ ST1: Elles oublièrent la source de cette aisance : debout la première, couchée la dernière. Toujours en train de travailler... (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 34).

Bâ TT1: They forgot the source of this easy life; first up in the morning, last to go to bed, always working. (Bâ, *So Long a Letter* 21).

In the Bâ ST1, Mariama Bâ uses a colon after the word « aisance » as a means of introducing further information that gives insights into what impact the « easy life. » The ellipsis at the end of the Bâ ST1 helps the reader by providing more context. Semantically, it emphasizes that the work of labor of the women probably has no end, that it is an ongoing, continual process.

One of the main questions is whether the colon in the Bâ ST1 plays a more nuanced role than usual in the context of the Bâ ST1 above. And the translator chooses to adapt the Bâ ST1 to English using a semicolon. Another issue is how to convey the relentlessness of women as exactly presented in the Bâ ST1: Both « toujours » and « en train » are already used in the Bâ ST1. But these were not sufficient for the source author in expressing her experience, as the speaker narrates the sociocultural realities of women's lives in their society. Therefore, introducing an ellipsis in the Bâ ST1 draws our attention to how women engaged in working regularly, daily, almost forever.

The mediator renders the ST1 in accordance with the punctuation norms of English by using a period—a domestication. Though related thoughts are linked together by the semicolon, there is a tendency for the English-speaking audience to overlook the emotional depth and sentiment tied to the ST1's ellipsis, since the translation does not include the ellipsis. Similarly, in the translation of Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë*, such examples of punctuation creating stylistic effects appear challenging.

Kane ST2: — Grand maître, le chef souhaiterait que vous lui fassiez l'honneur d'une visite, si vos hautes préoccupations vous en laissent le loisir. (Kane, *L'Aventure ambiguë* 41).

Kane TT2: “Great master, the chief hopes that you will do him the honor of a visit, if your high preoccupations leave you the leisure . . .” (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 30).

The Kane TT2 above is an instance where the translator introduces an ellipsis at the end of the translation. The ellipsis is absent in the authorial style of the Kane ST2. Generally, it can be argued that such a decision is influenced by the fact that the translator is used to the habit of Cheikh Kane using this punctuation often since the beginning of the novel. The translator attempts to predict or reinterpret the original author's voice and thus adapts the Kane ST2 with the introduction of an ellipsis, knowing that this action has no negative effect on the Kane TT2 audience, which can be

considered a foreignization of the punctuation because the ellipsis in the Kane TT2 replaces the period in the Kane ST2, creating a possible or potential open-ended break that is implicitly displayed in the character's speech. The Kane TT2 above can be compared with the Kane TT2 below.

Kane ST2: « La Parole doit continuer de retentir en lui, se dit-il. Il est de ceux qui ne cessent pas de prier, pour avoir refermé leur livre de prières. Dieu lui est présence constante... et indispensable. C'est cette présence, je crois, qui lui colle ainsi la peau sur les os du front, lui enfonce dans les orbites profondément excavées ce regard lumineux et calme. ... » (Kane, *L'Aventure ambiguë* 106).

Kane TT2: "The Word must continue to echo within him," the boy said to himself. "He is one of those who do not cease to pray when they have closed their prayer book. To him, God is a constant Presence—constant and indispensable. It is this Presence, I believe, which stretches the skin tight across the bones of his forehead, and sets that luminous and profound expression within the deep-cut orbits of his eyes. ..." (Kane, *Ambiguous Adventure* 94).

Here, Cheikh Kane introduces an ellipsis immediately after « constante » in the Kane ST2. Semantically, this ellipsis represents the weight of the adjective « constante » as used in the Kane ST2, giving it a literal duration across the space of the page. The ellipsis also emphasizes the length of such duration, and the length of how long the divine presence abides with the boy.

The translator's creativity involves the replacement of the ellipsis by a hyphen to connect the speaker's thoughts. Then, in order to accentuate the introspection or the frequent, unceasing nature of the presence of God as conveyed in the Kane ST2, the translator redoubles the adjective "constant" and places it right after the hyphen. This adaptation tends to respect the original author's

punctuation style, though in a visibly creative way. While the repetition of the adjective “constant” in the TT2 can be arguably critiqued as over-translation since the ST2 has no such repetition, it can draw the attention of the English-speaking audience to the weight placed on this adjective by the source text author.

Full Text Citation: Achodo, David. "Cultural Mediation: Challenges of Stylistic Translation in the Francophone African Novel." *Master's Thesis*, University of Tennessee, 2025.

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